

Enabling Interconnected Science Workflows through an Adapter Approach

Jesse McGaha, Marshall McDonnell, Lance Drane, Seth Hitefield, Gavin M. Wiggins, Gregory Cage,
Robert Smith, Mike Brim, Mark Abraham, Richard Archibald
and Addi Malviya-Thakur
Oak Ridge National Laboratory
Oak Ridge, TN USA

Abstract—The INTERSECT Software framework project aims to create an open federated library that connects, coordinates, and controls systems in the scientific domain. It features the Adapter, a flexible and extensible interface inspired by the Adapter design pattern in object-oriented programming. By utilizing Adapters, the INTERSECT SDK enables effective communication and coordination within a diverse ecosystem of systems. This adaptability facilitates the execution of complex operations within the framework, promoting collaboration and efficient workflow management in scientific research. Additionally, the generalizability of Adapters and their patterns enhances their utility in other scientific software projects and challenges.

Index Terms—messaging, internet of things, interconnected scientific workflows, adapters

I. INTRODUCTION

The INTERSECT SDK project [1], part of Oak Ridge National Laboratory’s Interconnected Science Initiative [2], is an open software framework for autonomous laboratories. It utilizes a system of systems and microservices architecture [3], facilitating seamless collaboration and efficient data sharing among labs. Various resources may be connected to the overall system to allow remote coordination of compute, instrument, data, and other systems. Each resource requires a control interface by which INTERSECT SDK may communicate with and send commands to the resource. These control interfaces are the INTERSECT SDK “Adapters”.

The name “Adapter” in INTERSECT SDK derives inspiration from the object-oriented programming (OOP) design pattern of the same name described in the seminal book, Design Patterns: Elements of Reusable Object-Oriented Software [4]. In OOP, the adapter design pattern allows incompatible interfaces to work together. This is usually done by creating the Adapter class that converts a given class into the form of another. Similarly, the INTERSECT SDK Adapter concept translates command and control communication from

a resource in the scientific ecosystem to messages that are understood by other Adapters in INTERSECT SDK. Within the INTERSECT SDK Software Development Kit (SDK), [1] there is a common, inheritable, core adapter class. This core adapter is extensible, a vital trait given the uniqueness of INTERSECT resources and the methodology by which they may be controlled. Future plans include open-sourcing the INTERSECT-SDK with this Adapter pattern included.

Adapters provide a flexible and extensible interface for diverse systems, enabling effective communication and coordination within INTERSECT. Leveraging Adapters allows for seamless integration and layering of multiple coordinating layers. These adapters and their patterns can be easily generalized to other scientific software projects and challenges.

II. OVERALL SYSTEM INTEGRATION

To connect a variety of systems, INTERSECT SDK implements a common messaging layer. Adapters act as converters between the directive within a message and the intended action by a system. Broad categories of messages (such as *request* or *status*) capture the general functionality of resources. An adapter receives a message, interprets it, and then implements the instruction against a given system. Because the Adapter carries the sole responsibility of communicating with the greater INTERSECT system and this functionality is captured in the common Adapter, extensions of an Adapter can be highly specialized to interact with complex systems.

These Adapters can then be incorporated into scientific workflows via the messaging layer commands. These workflows can be run using many different workflow management systems. Currently, no specific workflow system is used for INTERSECT. Future work in the INTERSECT software framework for adapters includes using workflow management systems to run adapter messages and also adapters that can connect workflow management systems into the ecosystem.

III. INTEGRATION OF CONTROL SOFTWARE

As there are no generalized interfaces common to all scientific equipment, a layer of abstraction is necessary between whatever software package is capable of managing a given device in an automated laboratory and the wider INTERSECT framework. Each kind of device, from the most general case for a compute resource to the most specific case of a

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Fig. 1. System Integration Structure

particular model of a particular brand of scientific instrument, requires its own extension of an adapter to create the structure demonstrated in Figure 1. The Adapter interfaces with that device’s individual control software, manages data ingress and egress from the resource to INTERSECT, and can describe that device’s capabilities to the rest of INTERSECT.

Resources, data, instruments, or others, that already possess methods of external interface require less extension efforts. An example of a more complex extension can be observed with the Adapter design in Figure 2 that was created to interface with Nion Swift, an open-source software “for the operation of Nion electron microscope instruments”. [5], [6] Nion Swift contains a rich suite of tools for controlling these microscopes and has begun implementing methods of external control; however, complete external control of the software required injecting commands into a currently running Nion Swift environment. To allow external access, a plugin was developed for Nion Swift to create remote procedure call (RPC) functionality that was paired with RPC control in the adapter extensions. This implementation allows the plugin to safely limit what features should be externally exposed, while also limiting changes required to connect and interact with the plugin to the adapter extensions.

Fig. 2. Adapter Structure

Resources more resistant to external connectivity hamper the adapter approach. Resources lacking API access, source code access, and other means of interfacing require increasingly more effort or resource customization to create access by which an Adapter could interface with a resource. The Nion Swift use case is one of many applications for using the

Adapter pattern for instrument and compute resources. For additive manufacturing, the adapter pattern is used to control 3D printing stages and to export thermal camera data. This experimental data is sent to Computation Adapters, such as in Figure 1, that perform simulations to help predict material properties and provide feedback on printing speed. For electric grid applications, the adapter pattern is used for hardware simulators which export data to larger-scale, digital “neighbor” simulations running again on Computation Adapters. The interaction between Adapters enables the distribution of tasks through the INTERSECT control plane, seen in Fig. 1.

IV. DISCOVERY OF ADAPTER CAPABILITIES

Programmatic communication of a system’s capabilities can be accomplished through a formal listing of messages an adapter is capable of accepting. Metadata can be defined for each of these messages to provide a description of the adapter’s behavior upon receipt of that message type. In the Nion Swift example, one endpoint would be an *action* type, *start* subtype message with content defining a scan for the microscope to perform. The metadata for this endpoint would describe the microscope’s procedure in a human-readable way. A separate INTERSECT discovery service will collect the provided metadata from each adapter and display the supported capabilities of each for a user. This process can be automated as in cases where a program searches for a compute node with an adapter to which it can send a computation job. Additionally, the list of capabilities provided could be displayed directly to a user to allow him to design a custom workflow.

V. LESSONS LEARNED

Creating a sufficiently diverse and flexible communication schema within the control plane without sacrificing interoperability is nontrivial and an ongoing effort. Resources resistant to interoperability drastically increase the level of effort required for adapter creation, which is a weakness noted in section III. Sufficient resistance to interoperability may render a given resource practically un-adaptable and unsuited for integration.

VI. CONCLUSION

INTERSECT software framework utilizes the concept of adapters to provide a standardized interface and a description of the capabilities. By exposing functionality through a system of messages of standardized types, Adapters are able to describe and expose their capabilities in a generalized and flexible way to cover a wide array of system or device types.

The integration of Adapter patterns within the INTERSECT software framework demonstrates the power of leveraging adapters for interconnecting science workflows. The adaptability of Adapters provides scientific software developers with a powerful tool to interconnect their own systems, promoting interoperability, collaboration, and efficient workflow management. As the scientific community continues to evolve, leveraging Adapter patterns will be crucial for creating interconnected ecosystems that advance scientific research and experimentation.

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